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DESIGNING THE TOTAL EXPERIENCE.

A MODEL FOR THE CHANGING ROLE OF THE DESIGNER

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a model for designing the total experience of a product, service or product-service system. In most research and models the user takes a central place. The so-called cone model also integrates strategic company concerns. The model shows what the role of the designer can be in order to create more meaningful products or services from a holistic perspective. It gives design thinking - defined in this context as 'creating added value at a strategic and conceptual level' - a natural place in the innovation process and it shows why the role of the designer will change rapidly in the coming years. In a world where products tend to commoditize, it becomes more and more difficult to create distinctive products solely through design, as in the tangible result. The brand and added meaning from context such as storytelling are sometimes equally as important to the product experience as intrinsic product features.

Keywords: design thinking, experience, emotion, product-service system, storytelling.

INTRODUCTION

There are a few underlying thoughts that evoked the need to capture the experience of a product from a holistic point of view instead of looking at fragmented pieces such as usability, brand experience or the different design disciplines that were involved to design the product. At the basis is the belief that the role of the designer has to shift, from designing as an act to acting as a problem solver: from doing to thinking. In a rapidly changing world, the role of the designers is changing, as is the place in the design process. As the needs of consumers change, so the needs of the industry must

also change. There are a few beliefs that form the basis of these assumptions.

CONTEXT

All the beliefs mentioned below have a direct or indirect influence on the role of the designer.

THE DIGITAL REVOLUTION

When we look back on the last 2 decades 30 years from now, it would not surprise me if we refer to it as the digital revolution. There are 2 main reasons that caused this digital revolution. The first reason was the fact that the price of fast microprocessors and solid state memory kept dropping and became affordable. This, and the fact that the speed of microchips and the capacity of the memory chips kept growing rapidly caused an accelerating effect regarding possible applications. The second reason was the emerging world wide web. From 1993, the web started to grow and to create this network of which we could only dream. When William Gibson's *Neuromancer* came out in 1984, it was inconceivable that part of it would be reality just 2 decades later. The web created almost unlimited access to information and knowledge, independent of time and place. It also made it easy to contact peers, a development that was propelled to an even greater extent by the rise of social media. These two developments exhibited major synergy. Increased processor speed made the web faster, so the content to be shared could become larger and more complex. The world has become transparent, which has had a major influence on the way we think and behave. It has even changed economic regulations. New knowledge is spread quickly and easily, and is accessible for everybody, at any time and any place.

The digital revolution also propelled the digitization of services. Processes that originally were carried out on paper, for instance transferring money or filling in your tax form, became available online or through mobile devices. In the case of mobile devices, they became a vital part of the product experience. It's hard to imagine the iPad having any value without the apps. There is no reason to believe that this digital revolution is over.

Another effect of this digital revolution was the digitization of the design profession itself. The engineering process of a simple plastic product like a pocket calculator could take weeks. You needed experience and making moulds - for instance - was expensive and not without risk. All these engineering processes have become much simpler, which benefits the freedom of creating the design and alternatives.

THE COMMODITIZATION OF PRODUCTS

At a functional level, mass-produced products or product features generally tend to commoditize very quickly. Products within a price category offer roughly the same benefits. This is the case for phones and cars, for instance. There are different reasons for each group of products, but it all comes down to the fact that it has been difficult for companies to claim either a knowledge advantage, a technical advantage, a distribution advantage or an economic advantage due to the world becoming transparent. This is one of the reasons why brands have become so important in order to gain a competitive advantage. A positive brand experience can create the difference. A brand reflects your personality or says something about the group to which you want to belong. A strong brand personality takes years to build and is hard to copy. Consumers trust you because of a perceived authenticity. It's possible to copy the Apple products or product features but it's hard to copy the brand values and personality and be trustworthy. A strong brand is hard to beat.

The total experience of the product is not only in the product but also in the brand that offers you the product. In many cases the storytelling aspect of the product has become equally as important as the product itself. The major western brands were already known before they entered the Chinese market, without the Chinese having the products

themselves. Ferrari is in everybody's mind, but who has actually driven a Ferrari?

USERS, CONSUMERS AND CLIENTS

In literature and education, the user of a product, service or product-service system is often hailed as not to be forgotten. As a design practitioner, I always have to interact with a client. Clients don't usually refer to users, but to consumers. The most important step for our clients is to sell the product. Of course, a consumer becomes a user and should become an ambassador of the product. But the state of mind of a consumer is quite different to that of a user. Using an anonymous product which has excellent characteristics is not a problem. For instance, using equipment or tools that are bought by your boss. But selling an anonymous product is quite complicated.

MANY SKILLED DESIGNERS

There are currently an estimated 1400 design schools in China alone, and the number of students is growing each year. When design became a true profession - sometime during the fifties and sixties - designers were hard to find and there was hardly any education, let alone a tradition in design education. During the last 3 decades, schools have developed and the overall quality of design education has improved. There's a lot of competition among young designers and there are no signs that this will decrease in the coming years. For designers it becomes important to question their role. What will be the added value of the designer in the future?

THE CONE MODEL

THE TOTAL EXPERIENCE

The model is created in design practice and takes four levels of entrepreneurship as its starting point: the enterprise, strategy development, concept development and design. Decisions at all these levels influence the consumer's experience of the product and/or service in a different way. The model aims for giving insights in order to create more coherent and therefore more meaningful products or product-service systems. The aim should be designing the total experience.

As designers, we want to play a vital role in the development of products and services. Traditionally, the designer is asked to 'design' the product or service; to create the tangible part of it, with which the user can interact. A lot of the thinking - strategy, brand development, among other things - has been done before. In the traditional way of working the designer is given a brief and creates the design. In recent years many people have started to question this working method. Tim Brown's book *Change by Design* contains many insights and examples, and explains why design is much more than creating a form. Many publications have been written on why a different view on design is valuable, but there aren't many models that encapsulate the 'thinking' and the 'doing' at once.

The central idea of this model is that decisions at every level of the innovation process influence the product experience. The model represents the whereabouts of a company, an undertaking.

Figure 1

At the top there is the entrepreneurship, the core that drives the company (figure 1). It often starts with a belief and goals that belong to this belief.

At the second level, strategy is defined, for instance by a strategist, brand developer or innovation manager. This is where direction for new products or services is developed. In most cases, the end result is a written piece, a brief.

At the third level, these strategies become more tangible in concepts. In general it comes down to defining interaction between the product and the consumer. The end result is often a combination of text and sketches.

At the 4th level, the actual designing takes place. This is where the product and all the features become definitive. It is the level at which the design disciplines operate.

Looking at the cone, the upper level gives input to the level below. In the classic way of designing that was taught 25 years ago, the design process looked like the process shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: the classic way

The designer was given a brief and he was then supposed to come up with a few alternative concepts, one of which would be chosen. He didn't have any influence on the strategy or company goals. His ability to create leverage was limited by the strategy brief.

Looking at the cone model, you can say that all the activities at the bottom are discipline oriented, while at the top they are discipline independent. You can also say that at the top it's more about thinking

and creating business, while at the bottom it's about doing and creating designs (figure 3).

Figure 3: from doing to thinking

In recent years it has been generally acknowledged that the development of strategies has a vital creative component to it (Tim Brown, among others) and that designers can play a role in this. Not only do they possess creative talents, they also have experience in connecting strategy to the actual design discipline. But what happens if designers start acting at a strategic level? To start with they can influence the whole innovation process. Their influence will increase which benefits the impact of the end result (figure 4). It will increase their footprint.

Figure 4: a bigger role for the designer

But there is an interesting side effect. Operating at the strategic level gives you the opportunity to 'move around'. You're not held back by the limitations of a design discipline (figure 5). And it could be that the direction that is defined as most promising ends up at an end result that's out of your comfort zone, in a discipline you're not trained in.

This is a direct consequence of the idea of design thinking.

Figure 5: out of your comfort zone

Why would we want this? I believe in designing the total experience: from product features to brand experience, from hardware to software. In my view, this is the only way to create competitive and coherent product-service systems.

THE EFFECT ON THE EXPERIENCE OF THE PRODUCT

Decisions are being made at all levels, and they all have an impact on the experience of the product (figure 6).

	WHAT DO THEY DEVELOP?	THE EFFECT ON THE USER / THE CONSUMER
1 entrepreneur	VISION / AMBITION / ECONOMIC VALUE / DREAMS	MEANING /
2 strategist	THE BRAND / PRODUCT STRATEGY / COMMUNICATION STRATEGY / DIRECTION	MEANING / EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE /
3 conceptualist	CROSSMEDIAL CONCEPTS / PRODUCT SERVICE SYSTEMS / INTERACTION	AESTHETICS / MEANING / EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE /
4 designer	PRODUCTS / SERVICES / COMMUNICATION / DESIGN	AESTHETICS / MEANING / EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE /

the total experience

Figure 6: the total experience

Dreams

The dreams of the entrepreneur or the board of the company can have a meaningful effect on the experience of a product. The maverick behaviour of Richard Branson influences the way we look at the products of Virgin. His 'challenging the establishment' attitude makes some people want to fly with Virgin Atlantic instead of British Airways.

Recently people have become very angry about the salaries of bankers after the financial crisis. They were perceived as unethical, although a lower salary for the directors would not influence the financial services at an instrumental level.

Direction

Strategic decisions influence the product experience in different ways. Decisions about the product range of a brand influence the way you feel, for instance about the car you bought. The top model of Audi is the R8. The owners of an Audi A4 might feel much more pride in driving an Audi, knowing that this cool R8 is the top model, rather than the A6. Being part of the family that 'owns' this cool car is meaningful for the user (figure 7).

Of course; strategic decisions also directly influence the user experience. Apple's decision to limit mechanical interaction for the iPhone and iPad as much as possible and to move all interaction towards the touchscreen had a big impact on the experience. It increased flexibility but also created a brand new tactile experience.

Figure 7: the Audi R8 Spyder

Interaction

The interaction of the product and/or service is defined at the conceptual level. This applies not only to the physical interaction, but also to the visual interaction or the way the brand is expressed in the product. In the concept phase, strategic input converges to a design of the interaction.

Design

The actual designing takes place at the fourth level. Needless to say that all the decisions made during the design process have an impact on the product experience. The product becomes tangible, touches all the senses and carries all the decisions made at

the levels above. Figure 8 and figure 9 are two good examples of how a company strategy is made tangible. In these cases it's about retail design. Needless to say which one is the price fighter and which one aims to sell a high end product.

Figure 8: Carpetland - Amsterdam, the Netherlands (photo by Lars van den Brink)

Figure 9: Janssen - Amsterdam, the Netherlands (photo by Lars van den Brink)

WHY THE DESIGNER?

The fact that decisions at all levels in the model have an impact on the experience of the product doesn't answer the question of why the designer should play a role in this. All design disciplines originally aim at designing intrinsic product features rather than designing the total experience. The only way to create a coherent and impactful product experience is first to create awareness of the impact of the decisions on all levels and second to start at the strategic level. By starting the design process at the strategic level, it is possible to follow a more integrated approach, taking into account meaning, aesthetics and emotional experiences. The designer has all the skills and talents to be the director of such a process. In most cases this part of the process is done within the company. Why then opt for a designer? To start with the designer is creative and should be able to enable this creativity at a higher level. Also: designers and creative people in general have the ability to challenge, which is a great characteristic in change processes. When the strategic and/of concept part of the design or innovation process is handled internally it's more difficult to challenge processes or decisions. Beside this, because of the experience with designing, the designer is able to connect all levels. He can take care of making the fit between goals, strategy and realization (design). In this way an innovation process can be approached from a more holistic point of view, and serve company concerns and user concerns. The benefit for industry is in better and more distinctive products and/or services. The benefit for the consumer/user lies in a more coherent product-service systems experience, such as a better embedding of branding in the product experience.

And what can the designer do to take this place? To start with it would be wise to embrace a multi-disciplinary approach. The designer of the future will be more a director in order to create relevance instead of 'just' designing.

THE FREITAG CASE

In 1993, Markus and Daniel Freitag, designed a messenger bag cut from an old water resistant truck

tarpaulin. The two brothers from Zurich Switzerland wanted a heavy-duty and water resistant bag. They got their inspiration from the colourful trucks on the highway, just in front the apartment where they lived. The graphics of the old tarpaulins are partly still visible on the bag. Every bag looks different but also unique. You can choose the one you like most. The carry belt is made from a second-hand car seat-belt, and bicycle inner tubes were used for the finishing of the edges. The idea of Markus and Daniel, graphic designers by training, was to make bags for themselves, but they ended up running a company with a staff of over 120 people, producing bags and other products like footballs. The Freitag brand is well known throughout the whole world. They have flagship stores in Berlin, Davos, Hamburg, Cologne, Vienna, New York and Zurich.

Figure 9: tarpaulins are cut

Figure 10: the iconic Freitag bag

They managed to create meaningful products from a holistic perspective. The strategy (especially the brand personality), the interaction and the product itself: they all fit to their dreams. Their strong and humorous visual identity gives expression to who they are and what the products can mean for you. Markus and Daniel created a great total experience for the buyers of their products by connecting all levels of the cone. They designed a brilliant strategy 'by accident'.

GIANT FLAGSHIP STORE

In 2008 the Dutch design agency Fabrique was asked to design a flagship store in Amsterdam for bicycle brand Giant. Giant is the biggest bike manufacturer in the world and in the Netherlands it's the number three in the market (after Batavus and Gazelle). The aim was simple: create a shop that fits the brand and makes a profit. The Giant brand is renowned for its innovative strength, its bold identity and leadership,

Traditionally, the shop owners are repairmen without much connection with modern retail. The shop-in-shops created awareness of the fact that displaying a bike creatively and arranging your shop properly can boost your turnover. The bike shop owners were also trained and the whole supply chain of bikes, accessories and clothing was reshaped to become an almost just-in-time delivery model.

The flagship store was the next step.

Fabrique was involved in decisions at all levels of the cone model. In fact at the start of the project there was no brief. During the first weeks we created the brief, together with the client. At the strategic level, the design company took decisions regarding the category management, target groups (more women), brand expression and the positioning, all in close cooperation with the client, Giant Benelux. Decisions taken at the strategic level formed the starting point for the development of the concept of the store. At the concept level additional services

Figure 11: the shop in the Van Woustraat, Amsterdam

were defined ('repair & go' and free coffee, among other things). The shop should have a focus on communicating the technical quality of the bikes. Also a different point of view was added: a bike is important as an expression of someone's identity, prospects should recognize themselves from a lifestyle point of view. A bike is more than a gadget to get from A to B. At the design level all this was translated into a brief with 3 focus points:

- It should be clear at a glance where to find which type of bike. Clients should be able to recognize 'their' type of bike which is more related to their lifestyle than to technical specifications. Therefore a set of giant visuals was created.
- Show the bikes as 'heroes'. So called 'catwalks' were designed in order to experience the (technical) beauty of the product. Some of them are mounted against the wall or upside down!
- Make accessories and clothing - especially female clothing - clearly visible.

Figure 12: the shop in the Van Woustraat, Amsterdam

The shop in the Van Woustraat in Amsterdam has a clear layout: on the left side of the entrance you can find all the city bikes, and on the right side the racing and mountain bikes are positioned. The aim was to create a quiet shopping environment with fewer bikes than normal. To be honest: up to now, it has been a challenge for the shopkeeper to find a balance between attractively displayed bikes and filling up the space with all the models Giant sells.

The rather large clothing and accessory department is in the back and is clearly visible, thanks to the natural light entering through the glass ceiling. The various segments are indicated by big visuals. Extra services, such as 'repair & go' and the free coffee, are clearly indicated.

Figure 13: the shop in the Van Woustraat, Amsterdam

The result of all this thinking and designing was a shop that not only in the first two years after opening performed 130% above target but also tells the story about the brand. The clothing department was extended and the shop attracts more women than normal. In short: the shop is a big success, and in the meantime a second flagship store has been opened in Hilversum.

CONCLUSIONS

The cone model presented in this positioning paper is a helpful model for creating a total experience that is coherent and powerful. A solid conversion from one level to the next is important in order not to lose sight of the highest ambition. The levels should be connected very carefully. It's a challenging thought to research the effectiveness of different types of conversion from one level to another. The Freitag case shows that entrepreneurship leads to a good, integrated brand experience where where company concerns and user needs meet each other. The Giant case shows that close cooperation between company and design consultancy on all levels can create a great experience and a solid business case at the same time.

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